

Original Research Article

SCHOOL PLANT MANAGEMENT SKILLS AND EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF PHYSICAL RESOURCES IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

Ibiene KALAGBOR-GBEKE

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education
Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Rivers State, Nigeria.
ibienekalagbor@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: The study examined school plant management skills and effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study which adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of 268 public secondary school principals in the state. A sample of 255 principals which constituted 95% of the population was drawn through the stratified random sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire tagged, “School Plant Management Skills and Effective Utilization of Physical Resources Questionnaire (SPMSEUPRQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument which contained 12 items was properly validated and the test-retest method was used to determine the reliability which yielded an “r” of 0.82 through Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that the school plant management skills, communication skills, cross-networking skills and maintenance skills, ICT skills, decision-making skills, communication skills, cross-networking skills and maintenance skills. The study also revealed that the ways school physical resources skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources include ensuring that physical resources are utilized based on the purpose for which they were provided and helping in the institution of adequate maintenance/utilization culture. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn and it was recommended among others capacity capacity-building programme on school plant management skills and effective utilization of physical resources should be provided to public secondary school principals by Rivers State Secondary School Management Board.

Keywords: School Plant, Management Skills, Effective, Utilization, Public Secondary Schools.

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INTRODUCTION

The roles of principals in public secondary schools require different types of skills for effective service delivery through adequate utilization of available resources. One of such important types of skills is the school plant management skills. The school plant described all the environment, facilities, equipment and buildings in which academic activities take place. It is the physical expression of the school and what it stands for. The school plant comprises of every other thing in the school except the human beings (human resources). The human resources in the school are not part of the school plant probably because they are superior and they coordinate the utilization of the various components of the school plant. School plant is an important resource on which school activities rest.

The management of the school plant involves the coordination of the utilization and maintenance of the various units or components of the school plant. It involves such activities

and processes as planning, organizing, directing and controlling the activities of other people towards the provision, utilization and maintenance of the school plant so that school goals can be achieved (Okoro, 2020). Effective utilization of physical resources implies the judicious utilization of these resources in a way that their life span is sustained and school goals are achieved. Public secondary schools are government-owned secondary schools. The school facilities in public schools are provided by the government and other public agencies. Secondary schools occupy a very important position in our school system. They supply middle-level manpower to our economy and they equally prepare students for higher or tertiary education. Possession of adequate school plant management skills will enhance the proper utilization and maintenance of physical resources. It will improve the quality of teaching and learning activities in public secondary schools (Nwokocha, 2019).

School plants are in a very deplorable state in some public secondary schools in Rivers State. We observe de-roofed buildings, sagging ceilings, cracked walls, broken chairs and tables, dusty and rough floors, leaking roofs and so on. It is on this note that it becomes imperative to investigate the school plant management skills needed by public secondary school principals for effective utilization of physical resources.

Statement of the Problem

School plant refers to all the facilities needed for the smooth take-off and sustenance of a school. It is a basic requirement for the establishment of any organization where teaching and learning will take place. Adequate provision of the school plant is cost-intensive and requires proper management skills for the school plant to last long and for school goals achieved. A visit to some public secondary schools in Rivers State speaks volumes about the school plant management skills of some principals. From the state of the school plant, one begins to wonder if these principals possess adequate school plant management skills. This situation impacts negatively on the school activities. The researcher is concerned by this, hence the need to examine the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate school plant management skills and effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Identify the school plant management skills needed by principals for the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Examine the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- What are the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
- What are the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the school plant management skills needed for the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopted the theory of quality management postulated by Williams Edward Denning in 1982. The theory of quality management according to Kpee (2015 p. 62) stated that “the responsibility for quality remains with the top management in any organization”. This implies that building up quality products (graduates) from the school system is the function of the principal and the secondary school management board. They do this by providing quality leadership and management of educational resources in their custody as well as by acquiring managerial skills that will enhance their productivity and service delivery. This theory is relevant to this study because if public secondary school principals have been equipped with adequate skills, especially school plant management skills, it will help them to adopt good facilities maintenance and utilization culture in their schools. This will enhance the quality of teaching/ learning activities and by extension, the quality of the schools’ products.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

School plants according to Kpee (2013), have been referred to several times as school or educational resources, school or educational materials or facilities. It is the hardware through which the educational curriculum (software) is transmitted to the group being educated (Agabi, 2004). School plant as defined by Mbipom cited in Akpan (2011) is the physical expression of school curriculum in the construction, inside and outside arrangement of buildings, facilities, equipment and open field around the buildings. It is the physical condition and general appearance of the whole school buildings, equipment and surroundings. School plants can be seen as paths, fields, playgrounds, classrooms, desks, school farms, school vehicles, flower beds, assembly halls, libraries, etc. Castaldi (1977) saw school plants as those things in education that help a conscientious teacher attain a height of teaching performance greater than what is possible without them. Teaching and learning facilities are numerous.

Any material that helps to facilitate instruction and understanding can be classified as part of a school plant or educational facilities. Jimoh (2005) stated that the school plant includes; the site, the buildings, tools and all the facilities of the school. It is the surroundings that advance the instruction processes while also protecting the physical well-being of the constituents. School plants have been classified by Oyebade (2009) as follows:

- **Buildings:** comprises of classrooms, offices, workshops, tuckshops, laboratories, libraries, sick bay, recreational facilities etc.
- Land on which buildings are erected.
- Equipment is installed in these buildings to enhance school learning activities.

- Machines, vehicles, furniture.
- Consumables.

A serene school environment provides a more conducive atmosphere for the academic process. School plants should be kept and maintained properly. The school facilities contribute greatly to the intellectual, social and moral progress of students (Akomolafe, 2001). The principal should constitute a school plant maintenance team. Three types of maintenance are common in educational institutions. They are preventive, corrective and emergency maintenance. These maintenance activities could be carried out through contracted services, in-house services and service on call. The principals as the chief executive officers in their schools are responsible for the effective management of the school plant. To do this, they need the following skills:

Leadership Skills: The central responsibility of principals is to guarantee that school goals are achieved. Leadership according to Ololube (2024) is the ability to influence people's behaviour so that they will work towards given objectives. Strong leadership skills are very much required to achieve set school objectives.

ICT Skills: As facilities managers, principals require proficiency in ICT literacy. This is necessary because facilities managers the world over are becoming more reliant on ICT technology. The more ICT skills the principal possesses, the more he is exposed to versatile software that is very useful in facilities management. The ability to use this software will be an advantage to the school manager because technology plays a vital role in how facilities run.

Decision-Making Skills: The power to make quick decisions in a confident and precise way is a skill school principals need to master in managing school facilities properly. The school manager is expected to make good and firm decisions. For decisions to yield the desired result, the decision maker needs to possess good decision-making skills and be less emotional and unbiased about the issues to be resolved (Ovwigho, 2004).

Communication Skills: The principals interact with many people every day. They engage with their staff, school board members and contractors. Their strong communication and interpersonal skills are an advantage. Principals understand and motivate team members and positively influence them. As principals, it is important to encourage and inspire teachers to achieve set objectives and goals of their schools. These skills are fundamental and can be developed and enhanced through capacity development programmes.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population comprised 268 principals (217 male and 51 female) of public secondary schools in the 23 LGAs of Rivers State. A sample of 255 principals (204 male and 51 female) was drawn via stratified random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire entitled, "School Plant Management Skills and Effective Utilization of Physical Resources Questionnaire (SPMSEUPRQ)" was used for data collection. The questionnaire which contained 12 items designed to elicit information for answering the research questions was properly validated by experts in research, measurement and evaluation. A modified four-point Likert rating scale was used in structuring the questionnaire items. The test-retest process and Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient were used to ascertain the internal consistency of the questionnaire

which yielded an 'r index of 0.82. Two hundred and fifty-five (255) copies of the instrument were administered and 240 copies were retrieved by the researcher with the help of two trained research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at a .05 significant level.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What are the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Statistical Analysis of School Plant Management Skills Needed by Principals for Effective Utilization of Physical Resources in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	Problem-solving skill is part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.17	1.49	Agree
2.	Leadership skills are part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.54	1.08	Agree
3.	ICT skills are part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.58	1.05	Agree
4.	Decision-making skill is part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.08	1.35	Agree
5.	Communication skill is part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.15	1.49	Agree
6.	Cross-networking skill is part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.15	1.37	Agree
7.	Maintenance skill is part of the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.	3.20	1.37	Agree
Aggregate Mean		3.265		

The result in Table 1 reveals that principals require all the school plant management skills considered in this study as their mean scores far exceed the criterion mean score of 2.50. The table shows that ICT and leadership skills are very important skills needed by principals in school plant management and effective utilization of physical resources as they ranked first and second respectively. Data in Table one show that the male and female principals agreed on items number 1 to number 7 as the school plant management skills needed by principals for the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The aggregate mean score of 3.265 for both male and female principals showed that they unanimously agreed on the items. Therefore, the school plant management skills needed by principals for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State include Problem-solving skills, leadership skills, ICT skills, decision-making skills, communication skills, and cross-networking skills and facilities maintenance skills.

Research Question Two: What are the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Statistical Analysis of the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD.	Remarks
8	Physical resources are utilized based on the purpose for which they were provided.	1.38	1.37	Agree
9	School plant management skills help school principals guide against overutilization of physical resources in their schools	3.43	1.16	Agree
10	School plant management skills help principals to ensure that physical resources are cared for/well preserved	3.30	1.29	Agree
11	School plant management skills enable school principals to institute an adequate culture of maintenance of physical facilities to enhance their effective utilization.	3.37	1.21	Agree
12	School plant management skills of school principals enhance the effective utilization of physical resources by ensuring that the utilization of physical resources is properly supervised.	3.15	1.16	Agree
13	Aggregate Mean	3.286		Agree

The result in Table two shows that all the male and female principals who responded to the questionnaire items agreed on all of them as the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State. All the items in Table two recorded mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 hence, they were accepted as the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources. School plant management skills help school principals to guide against overutilization of physical resources and school plant management skills help principals to institute an adequate culture of maintenance of physical facilities to enhance their effective utilization were the major ways school plant management skills enhance effective utilization of physical resources as they ranked first and second respectively.

The aggregate mean of 3.29 for both male and female principals showed that they had a common perception about the ways schools' plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in their schools. Therefore, school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources by ensuring that physical resources are utilized based on the purpose for which they were provided, they help school principals to ensure that physical resources are cared for and are well preserved; they help in the institution of adequate culture of maintenance which enhances effective utilization of physical resources and they help to ensure that utilization of physical resources is properly supervised.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the school plant management skills needed for effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: t-test analysis of school plant management skills required by Principals for effective utilization of physical resources

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Df	Calculated t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	189	3.25	1.28	238	.144	.662	Not significant
Female	51	3.29	1.39				

Data presented in Table three show the summary of the t-test analysis on the significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the school plant management skills needed for the effective utilization of physical resources in public

secondary schools in Rivers State. The result in Table three reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals' perception of the school plant management skills required by principals for effective utilization of physical resources as the calculated t-value is within bounds of the critical p-value. The z-value of .144 is less than the p-value of .662. Based on this, the null hypothesis was retained.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Df	Calculated t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	189	3.29	1.36	238	.138	.498	Not significant
Female	51	3.28	1.29				(Accepted)

Data presented in Table four shows the summary of t-test analysis on the significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals on the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The results in Table 4 reveal that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female principals' perception of the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources as the calculated t-value is within bounds of the critical p-value. The t-value of .138 is less than the p- p-value of .498. Based on this, the null hypothesis was accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research study identified seven school plant management skills that might be needed by principals in public secondary schools in Rivers State for effective utilization of physical resources. The school plant management skills considered were: problem-solving skills, leadership skills, ICT skills, decision-making skills communication skills, cross-networking skills and maintenance skills. The results of the analysis with mean scores and standard deviation revealed that all the school plant management skills selected were needed by principals for the effective utilization of physical resources. The major responsibility of school principals is to ensure that school goals are achieved through effective teaching and learning supported by proper management of available educational resources. School principals are often confronted with very challenging issues that require critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This is very necessary because they must find solutions to issues militating against effective teaching and learning. They require strong leadership and communication skills to enable them to coordinate the utilization and maintenance of physical resources in the school. Proper management and utilization of school facilities at this time when funding for education is becoming a very big problem is very important.

Proper management and utilization of available school facilities will help the school to maximize the benefit of having such facilities. Principals as school facilities managers require ICT skills and decision-making abilities. ICT is very relevant in having access to information. School managers can take advantage of this skill to access information such as models of different types of school equipment, models of maintenance procedures and guidelines on the utilization of certain school facilities that can be obtained online. The

principal can store an inventory of the school facilities on the computer as well as their maintenance schedule. He also needs to make decisions on the types of maintenance that need to be carried out on the several school facilities from time to time in order to increase their durability and usefulness. The findings of this study on managerial skills required by principals for effective utilization of physical resources are supported by Ogunyejo (2008) and Ololube (2024). These scholars outlined the skills required by a good educational manager to include among others the following skills: analytical- listening skill, communication skill, decision-making skill, problem-solving skill, leadership skill and human relations skill. They considered these skills as core skills in management and supervision which are major responsibilities of school principals. Senior secondary schools management Board and the State Ministry of Education can enhance the plant managerial abilities of public secondary school principals by organizing capacity-building programmes that will bridge these skills gaps in the principals.

The study also revealed the ways school plant management skills enhance the effective utilization of physical resources in public secondary schools in Rivers State including ensuring that physical facilities are utilized based on the purpose for which they were provided; helping school principals to guide against overutilization of physical resources; helping principals to ensure that physical resources are cared for and are well preserved; helping in the institution of adequate maintenance culture and proper supervision of the utilization of physical resources. These are very important because most schools do not have enough of these resources, therefore available ones should be optimally utilized and managed.

In schools where the principals possess adequate school plant management skills, the school plant components are properly maintained and utilized unlike where the reverse is the case. These findings are supported by Ozochi (2010), Igwebuike (2016) and Oyebade (2009). These scholars in their various studies outlined the various ways school plant management skills of a principal would likely enhance the effective utilization of educational resources that are available in their school. They linked school plant management skills to the effective utilization of educational resources and the academic performance of students. Therefore, school plant management skills positively impact the utilization of physical resources and the academic performance of students.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that public secondary school principals in Rivers State need problem-solving skills, leadership skills, ICT skills, decision-making skills, communication skills, cross-networking skills and maintenance skills for efficient and effective school plant management and utilization of physical resources. These vital skills are not commonly displayed by most principals hence the poor management of school plants and the inefficient utilization of physical resources in so many public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following were recommended by the researcher:

- A capacity-building programme on school plant management skills and effective utilization of physical resources should be provided to public secondary school principals by the Rivers State Secondary Schools Management Board.
- The government should make more money available for capacity-building

programmes for principals of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

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